

Radical Decentering Towards Self Directed Learning in the AI Knowledge Sharing and Employing Duolingo Application and Methods

Simila B, Research Scholar, PG and Research Department of English, Holy Cross College (Autonomous), Nagercoil-4. Affiliated to Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abishekapatti, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, India.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-0744-7187>

Dr. R. Abilasha, Assistant Professor, PG and Research Department of English, Holy Cross College (Autonomous), Nagercoil-4. Affiliated to Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abishekapatti, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, India.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5300-8928>

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Abstract

Structuralism laying its station on structures and systems had entangled the nation to look at its meanings and identities created out of vibrant intellectually bound minds. Intellectual standard of society goes unnoticed out of a systematized stable footed living. The theoretical boundary reserved is broken in post structuralism. Instead of binding one to the rules and regulations set, the rational sensibility in word and thought links one with the society that recreates all that are stable. This interlinking is carried over by technology. Self-Directed Learning through Duolingo makes inefficiency efficient. Easy handy application compact with the development of Language skills in AI assistance would make a student dive independently against the restricted gorges. This paper is an eye opener to the education system already prevailing and the standard students try to achieve. Hence, the opinion of the students on the methods of language learning amidst boredom created out of physical classroom and the teacher is deeply analyzed and evaluated for the well-being of the students.

Keywords: Decentering; AI Integration; Self Directed Learning, Duolingo.

Introduction

Decentered writings are independent intelligent gradations. They don't derive out of the Centre that keeps rotating to ever subjugate the development of thought but better handle the intelligence in accordance with one's systematical way of thought process. As denoted above, the very world that received the textual longings as treasure today looks it as pleasure. To state sarcastically, mere entertainment is the strength of education at present. Teaching to be played upon, booksthrown off, and question papers used to make paper cranes, ships and rockets. The very depth of education is in question due to the empowerment of technology. Computer Assisted Instruction, ICT enabled classrooms, blended mode of learning, flipped classrooms all are the demands of education. In such a scenario given birth is self-paced learning. The role of teachers here is limited and unexplainable. The methods of teaching using head now make the methods of teaching dead. Computer aided instruction looks at self-directed learner than a conventionally bound classroom groomed student and methods.

Decentered Literature Review

Mastered methodological mentality could live to locate a nation of dependence. The productivity expected out of it is very less. Rigidity of resources and binary oppositions leaves nothing newer and admirable. It enforces laws and bounds one with the established norms. Guided in the light of structuralist principles the world recognizes something beyond

that is still in its recourse. The practice that leads one to the core theoretically established social norms, looks back only at the treasures left by the predecessors than the living legends. The legendary characters taking its shape in different forms will insurg is inconceivable.

Poststructuralism waking up the nation that create identities and meanings, structures, languages and systems do not only lead towards surmountable developments breaking open insurmountable that crouches the society but also leaving in its meanings multiple unimaginable bases that is possible. Impossibility made possible through structures of stagnation. Living with essential commodities make a person immersed with the goods available in hand and reachable but a person striving for something beyond the arch looks deeper as to find the hidden treasure which can be approachable if one comprehends the meanings one after the other. Poststructuralists dig at this. The more they dig, the more deeper the meanings and boundaries cloistered lifts its bolts to give way to fresher and never experienced and popularized terms that purifies the society and its conventional life style. Derrida states:

The center is at the center of the totality, and yet, since the center does not belong to the totality (is not part of the totality), the totality has its center elsewhere. The center is not the center. The concept of centered structure although it represents coherence itself, the condition of the epistēmē as philosophy or science -- is contradictorily coherent. And as always, coherence in contradiction expresses the force of a desire. The concept of centered structure is in fact the concept of a play based on a fundamental ground, a play constituted on the basis of a fundamental immobility and a reassuring certitude, which itself is beyond the reach of play. (89)

Conceptual situational meanings derive out of poststructuralism. One singular word can intertwine one with the unnoticeable that may critically analyze to welcome into the standardized and labelled, the cultural social religious intermingling. When Jacques Derrida through his seminal lecture “Structure, Sign and Play in the discourse of the Human Sciences” plays with words and its intellect, Michael Foucault plays with the entire knowledge system. Julia Kristeva’s intertextuality and interconnectedness to the knowledge sharing in textual boardings are the values that review and retain and reshare the content that keeps floating.

The brain that restored what is taught in the physical classroom and had not the additional capability developing thinking to process inherent ideas, at the contemporaneous age not bothering about the teaching in the classrooms looks for the ideas to develop in its own. There is no botheration as to the effect that may remodel the ideas already there in intellect. Having trusting oneself completely one could accumulate the wealth surrounding within hours, there are many a student’s lost. The upliftment through aids too is forsaken for the better world that may lead to immeasurable uprising. This resurgence is expected not only from students but also from common folk with knowledge sharing out of computerized technical knowledge.

Technological Integration in Self Directed Learning

Language Learning that had expressed its concern over LSRW, as it is of four letters had remained in the four little corners of the language classroom. Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing had to struggle in a classroom while the teacher-oriented teaching learning blocked self-realization and the output that can be the centre of one’s external affairs. The nursed wisdom going barren bore no fruit in the midst of boredom. There is not a place left to retain the strength afforded of the language challenges in the classroom teaching. The emptied head looks at and accepts gem as hopeless as there is no practicality to entertain.

Teachers' continued teaching observed by the students to be subjective and dominative. Their modern thought mocks at the textual standard and the teachers' ability. In such a state it receives wholeheartedly a self honoured technology that can still entertain them.

Open Educational Resources (OER) are teaching and learning materials that are freely available online for everyone to use, whether you are an instructor, student or self-learner. Examples of OER include: full courses, course modules, syllabi, lectures, homework assignments, quizzes, lab and classroom activities, pedagogical materials, games, simulations, and many more resources contained in digital media collections from around the world. (Thamarasseri; Swayam ICT Module 24)

Self-paced learning starts here where there is acknowledgement of fun and joy. There are many applications that provide language fluency in fingertips. Wordwall, Chatgpt, Kahoot, Classpoint, Duolingo, Copilot AI, Blooket, Wayground as AI gamification tools can better provide self-directed learning without the guidance of the teachers. Even in classroom or out of the classroom students can learn at their own pace and interest. The more they engage with such application, the better they enhance in learning. Class centered teacher's role die as the students create meanings and identities and language roles with the native language influenced applications involved AI teachers. Colloquialism and the culturally, politically and religiously sided teacher perish to give birth to a technology self-centered legend to wake up. As noted in Maurice Gibbons' "The Self-Directed Learning Handbook: Challenging Adolescent Students to Excel",

SDL ends not in exercises but in action, and action as often as possible in the world beyond the classroom. Teachers do not direct students so much as they teach them to direct themselves by empowering them. SDL students work closely with other students and adults, not just independently. They are charged to learn academics, but are challenged with much more as well.(4)

Language Learning Duolingo: Web Application

Duolingo is one such platform discussed for the study to evoke curiosity in the students to learn the language at their convenience and compliance. It is comprised of 44 languages to study. Duolingo app provides interactive quizzes, developing the reading capacity, listening skills developed upon the native tongue and systematic writing ability to pace with the listening speed. The scoring upon completing each task provided interestingly leads one to the other sections. Instead of students deteriorating with games, this language study interconnects students with the friends in competition. The leaderboard shows if one has scored more than his friend in control with the same task. Such a style of learning of language develops LSRW skills. The struggle faced for years of study made easy with AI powered language applications. Grammatical errors and spelling corrections are identified and spotted. The importance of language in each word, phrase and sentence is made known to the practitioners of language in Duolingo. One thing to be noted; it is provided free of cost and one can learn the language correctly at his own speed. Additional chances also given to wind up the task expediently.

Research Focus through Tabular Study

The research paper tries to solve the research problem discussed of second language teaching learning using the quantitative methodology very poignantly. Students' multifaceted approach to the teaching of language in the English language classroom using interpretive, appreciative and analytical technological integration lives to open up the physical classroom that restricts open gestures for language development. The mentality of the present UG students to the acclimatization of ICT enabled AI tooled classroom stretches a way to look at

the other side of education that may live to challenge the conventional type of education all these years. The questionnaire circulated among students highlights the impact made even in the inner recesses of the student mentality.

The questionnaire was circulated through Google form for the reachability of the information so that the self-directed learning boosted up anyone seated in the cornered world with technology. Out of 200 students who responded to the Google form of questions, 30 students were randomly selected to finalize upon the impact of Duolingo in helping them to better learn the English language self-sufficiently away from the clutches of adoptive teaching learning. The topic under discussion for the paper after a careful examination of the questionnaire are understanding literary theories for the decentered meanings, students' views on language learning in and out of the classroom, digital learning methods used by them and the usefulness of language learning app like Duolingo that leads to the self-directed learning amidst AI influence of information generation. The lethargy gets dissolved through a handy application that interestingly leads for language fluency.

Table 1: Empirical study of Students' Responses to Language Learning and Digital Education
Sample Size: 30 Students (UG)

Category	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Understanding of Literary Theories	8	12	5	3	2
Views on Language and Learning	9	13	4	3	1
Opinion on Digital Learning Methods	10	11	4	3	2
Usefulness of Language Learning Apps (Duolingo)	11	12	4	2	1

Image 1: Percentage Wise Impact on the Understanding of Digital Education

Results and Discussion

The study details the core of decentered writings, the students' opinion on English language learning and its importance in them, the digital divide that united all in the same workplace called technology, the steady progress in language made through the guidance of AI enhanced Duolingo, developing in students the strength to meet the competitive world and leading internationally to set standard. 40% of the students agree upon the self-directed learning beneficial in developing LSRW and 27% strongly agree to the growth in advanced level digital app that takes over the teacher's role to guide on to the next levels to comprehend meanings and recreate self-mentored identities. 17% being neutral accept the role played by digital language and the learning adopted individually amidst the cloistered technological orientation. The student's ability to respond to the topic under discussion contributes to a better understanding of sub topics in table by going through a valid quantitative analysis. The response of the students indeed validates the classroom that is handled by teachers and the effort needed on the part of the teachers and learners for further invaluable involvement in AI powered applications that could develop the LSRW skills of the students. The students' support in the arguments reinstated strikingly the primary struggle faced by the students. Many of them eager to know about one such application that could develop their second language skill faster and without much effort.

Only 10% of the students disagree as the digital education is a bit far away from them as their local set up doesn't allow them to accommodate such a world of education. They denote their helpless state in handling such apps independently without the help of the teachers. Hence their response remains inconsistent. 7% strongly disagree as they hadn't understood the seriousness of the problems pertaining to the student community of AI technology. But the Pie diagram hopefully leads the students to a focused study plan for the successful completion of the tasks provided in the Duolingo app. The unaware are alerted on such app that may drive them to their own world undisturbed. Teacher centered listening, speaking, reading, writing becomes learner centered. The teacher fosters nurturing in the students through multiple roles as teacher and as facilitator. The struggle to bring up a better second language learner single handedly now falls upon the shoulders of the learner who is curious to support with the app that helps correct now and then mistakes made. A one-to-one correspondence is built between the application and the learner thereby it keeps the learner more engaged and not to go desperate of the simple mistakes made. It doggedly keeps in touch with the learner solving the issues of language learning; never like the teacher who admonishes for inattention and inability.

One may say that there may be technical difficulty in handling such educational method since everything involved happens with one single application. But one thing to be monitored here is the support that one gets out of the physical classroom. The very teacher who was the complete control peacefully takes rest while the student can balance with such application. The absence of the teacher or the center's vacant seat gets filled up with a restless ever bothered mentor AI that looks only at the positivity of the student. Continuous encouragement received amidst the vacuum left by the teacher fills up the gaps left emptied of. In such a state even the under developed, low graded communicator rises up to encounter the world AI powered confidently. The additional support of the app supplies what is left unpolished and unshaped. This is carried out only through self-directed learning techniques.

Conclusion

Ascending than descending through decentering of contents are the effect produced. Language rigidly taught bring innarrow methods of teaching and narrow-minded student

community. Language should have its capacity to build relationships across. Duolingo plays a vital role in communicating in the native tongue to reach the students digitally interconnected and claustrophobic in adjoining with teaching interference in the physical classroom. The fear of technology broken down as virtual blending of education houses the weaker and the stronger together in a single platform for language learning. The student is not as that of one who timidly stood before a center that kept everything in one place and with one single person. The structure bounces back at the center leading to recognize the level of learning already there, so that independence and technology meet at one place. The pestering on the part of the teacher minimized thus. The huddles in the path of second language learning smashed through Duolingo.

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